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Optical Sensory Networks in Soft Mechanical Composites

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Highly deformable soft structures are difficult to sense and control

A problem with using highly deformable soft structures in soft robotics or medical devices is that they are difficult to control due to their ability to change shape. Common ways to solve or get around this problem include adding strain limiting layers to lower degrees of freedom, adding sensors to measure their simplified shape (like a uniform curvature) or adding skins to the surface. However this takes away from the usefulness of these structures.

b Finger bends in 1 direction, curvature sensing

Truby, Ryan L., et al. *Advanced Materials* (2018)

Sensing skins measure touch and deformation

Zhao, Huichan, et al. *Science Robotics* (2016)

Sarwar, Mirza Saquib *Science advances* (2017)

Park, Yong-Lae, et al. *Journal of Micromechanics and Microengineering* (2010)

Biology shows high density integration of mechanoreceptors in skin and muscle ($\sim 1414 \text{ cm}^{-2}$ [1]) for sensing [2]. We take inspiration from nature and previous work with machine learning for soft foam proprioception [3] to embed a high density ($\sim 1 \text{ cm}^{-2}$) of optical deformation sensors within a soft composite to measure the state of deformation with machine learning.

We choose to use soft optical cores as deformation sensors

We chose optical sensors because they:

- Have low hysteresis
- Are resistant to changing environments (ex: in water, exposed to high magnetic fields, etc)
- Can carry more information than wires

We used a stretchable core material (Crystal tec (TPU), failure after 1000% strain) with similar properties to the scaffold so that the mechanical properties did not change much

Our sensors work by coupling light between lightguides when deformation causes them to touch

Our solution is a soft optical lightguide network we call optical lace (OL) embedded into a soft structure. Instead of using each lightguide as its own sensor, we use the interaction between multiple lightguides to sense deformation

- In the case shown on the right, an air gap separates the output cores from the input core, keeping the light in the input.
- When a deformation causes the 2 cores to touch, light couples

Combine the optical lace with a soft scaffold and we have a soft composite with sensing capabilities

We have shown that we can measure position...

With the same simple geometry as before, a deformation between outputs can cause contact with multiple outputs which allows us to calculate the position of the external contact using a ratio of the coupled light intensities between neighboring outputs.

- If the contact point is closer to the left, then the output to the left of the contact point will have more coupled light than the right

... and magnitude of deformation

We measured coupled transmission between 2 lightguides as they were pressed together with changing contact length (L_c) or contact width (W_c) (characterized by the distance between core centers). From this, we determine that a change in contact area between the 2 cores caused by deformation can be used to measure magnitude of the deformation

Constant contact width, changing length

Constant contact length, changing width

We have previously used this sensor to measure position and magnitude of uniaxial compression

We used OLs to measure the position of single and multiple external touches

We used OLs to measure the local compression every 2.2 mm in a cylinder

To get to more complex deformations, we use machine learning

For the rest of this presentation, we are using the following 2 geometries within a rectangular block. We change the design so that we can measure many types of deformation (twisting, bending, tension, compression) in different areas of the block. In the 2 images below, we show the geometries with the input lit up in blue and output in red.

Fabricated 3D printed soft scaffold with lightguides innervated after

We use the carbon M1 to print a soft polyurethane lattice with internal channels. Once printed and post processed, we thread the lightguides through and attach electronics (LED and photodiodes). The lightguides and electronics are held together with friction fit 3D printed parts so there is little noise from the connection.

Previously shown geometry

Block to be used for the rest of this presentation

Complete block with some of the sensors lit up for visualization

The block has 4 input cores (lit up in blue) and 11 output cores (5 of them lit up in red) innervating it. While there are 4 input cores. In the rest of the images, none of the cores will be lit up since we use IR for signal.

All inputs

5/11 outputs

All inputs and 5/11 outputs

To take the training data, we made a testing rig that can twist the block in different areas

The training rig has 3 DOF: twisting (-61° to 61°), bending (-81° to 81°), and ring position.

Ring position changes where the twist or bend happens

Twisting and ring position data taken plotted using t-SNE to visualize in 2D

Twist angles: -61 – 61 degrees in 6.7 degree intervals
Ring positions: 0 – 94 mm in 8.6 mm intervals

Training data set: 50,160/100,320 pts for each sensor

20 data points taken at each of 19 twist angles is 1 cycle

11 twist angle cycles taken for each of 12 ring positions

With t-distributed stochastic neighbor embedding (t-SNE), the data for the 11 sensors looks like > where each color is a different angle or ring position and the distance between them is how different the 11 sensor values are for each time stamp. Ideally each there would be tight clusters that are far apart from other clusters.

Machine learning algorithms tried

1. Decision tree
2. Random forest – lots of small decision trees , most common answer among smaller trees is the overall answer
3. Regressor chain – if 2 signals not independent, determine twist angle before ring position
 - First determine twist angle with random forest method, then conditionally predict ring position with random forest
4. Gradient boost regression – take a relatively simple model (decision tree) and add things to it wherever there is large deviation from data to minimize error
 - Look at errors after each tree is added and add new, separate tree and weight the results based on optimizing loss function using gradient descent
5. Polynomial fitting – fit a n^{th} order polynomial to the data
 - Need to be careful to not overfit so stuck to 3rd and 4th order polynomial

$$\text{Tree 1} * w_1 + \text{Tree 2} * w_2 + \text{Tree 3} * w_3 + \dots = \text{result}$$

Summary of results for each method

Model	Twist Angle Training RMSE (degrees)	Twist Angle Testing RMSE (degrees)	Ring Position Training RMSE (mm)	Ring Position Testing RMSE (mm)
Decision Tree	6.9	26.4	8.8	24.27
Random Forest	6.3	25.2	8.9	21.64
Regressor Chain	5.7	23.5	9.82	25.13
Gradient Boost	16.0	18.9	15.83	21.85
Polynomial (3 rd order)	19.5	23.5	24.56	24.49

The training columns means how well the model does when shown the data used to train it and the testing columns are how well the model does when shown never before seen, new data.

Overall gradient boost worked the best, although what works best for twisting angle may not work best for ring position as random forest shows slightly better results.

Future work

- Improve accuracy for twist and ring position:
 - Combine algorithms (ex: use different algorithms for twist and ring position)
 - Try other algorithms like neural nets
 - Change the hardware (ex: add more sensors)
- Do the same for bending and combined twisting and bending
- Use neural networks to do model predictive control or other control schemes

References

- [1] Mancini, Flavia, et al. "Whole-body mapping of spatial acuity for pain and touch." *Annals of neurology* 75.6 (2014): 917-924.
- [2] <https://nba.uth.tmc.edu/neuroscience/m/s2/chapter02.html>
- [3] Van Meerbeek, et al. "Soft optoelectronic sensory foams with proprioception." *Science Robotics* 3.24 (2018): eaau2489.

Acknowledgements

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